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Abstract

India reports millions of investment and revenue in the import and export of textiles but Muslim artisans occupy the lowest segment due to their strata and social milieu. They are often left behind and forgotten in the artisanship in a heavily decentralised and unorganised industry like Zardozi. Muslim men and women have contributed towards sustaining the art of Zardozi yet are majorly marginalised from inclusively participating in nation-building activities or entitlements as artisans. Zardozi, an art with such courtly culture and aesthetics, is currently on the verge of extinction. The hypothesis is that Zardozi is a male-dominated art but there are women working in silos that have been neglected and deprived of their due wages and acknowledgement. These Muslim women work equally hard, if not more, to sustain households and support their husbands, and yet are largely unaccounted for in the ecosystem of Zardozi. Work requires excruciating long hours of intricate labour with the thread and needle causing pain and numbness, especially for women who have double domestic burdens. While men work in Karkhanas (workshops), women are restricted to operating within homes and are paid disparately lower wages compared to their counterparts. Patriarchal customs deter them from engaging with the market directly, depriving them of financial independence and equal participation. Young girls, who are activated early to contribute to income generation along with leading domestic duties, often drop out of formal schooling post-puberty, are married off and confined to four walls fostering dependency on their husbands and families. These are the missing Muslim women of Zardozi. In recent years, there has been a resurgence of interest in Zardozi embroidery, with designers and artisans working to preserve and revitalise this traditional art form which has found its way into contemporary fashion and home decor. Despite these and other efforts by the government, there is a sincere need to protect these artisans by ensuring entitlements and support in the form of benefits, training and access to markets especially in clusters of Uttar Pradesh (UP) and Delhi that have been left behind in schemes of the “One District-One Product” (ODOP) and others. The paper assesses the socio-economic conditions of Muslim women artisans from the lens of Zardozi and relies on empirical findings, case studies, primary and secondary

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data to decode perceptions, challenges and opportunities within the ambit of Muslim women engaged as Zardozi artisans in the rural and semi-urban slums of UP and Delhi.

Keywords: Zardozi, Zarodozi workers, artisans, female Zardozi artisans, Muslim women

I. Introduction

Embroidery work is one of the key sources of income that sustains many households in the Indian economy. Next to pastors and farmers, the manufacturing industry notes one of the highest participation of the unorganised workforce in the country. In that sense, embroidery is the thread that serves both the rich and the poor. While for the rich, it is a possession of pride; for the poor, it is a source of sustenance and livelihood.

The economic studies of textiles have grappled with the extent to which traditional weavers and spinners were made extinct through deindustrialization and then reindustrialization of the urban centres (Riello & Roy, 2011). On one hand, while liberalized markets have positioned handicrafts as a desired commodity in the global village, on the other hand, they have shirked the domestic market for handicraft products through the heavy influx of machine-made products, resulting in the exclusion of artisans from their traditional skilled occupations and being forced to search for alternative livelihoods. (Majeed, 2019)

Zardozi is a thriving means of income generation in many Muslim-dominated parts of India. Bylanes in the cities and slums of Farrukhabad, Lucknow, Calcutta, Mumbai, and Delhi still hold the history that is full of grandiose and glitter. Handicrafts is one of the key trade segments with significant contributions coming from Uttar Pradesh (Planning Commission, 2019). Juxtaposing the craft's royal history, the plight of local artisans, especially Muslim women, is marred with economic distress and a lack of inclusive opportunities. Places of cultural significance like Lucknow, Delhi, or Farrukhabad still have Muslim communities living in hamlets and united by the threads of Zardozi.

Embroidery has always been a female-focused artform. In the case of Zardozi, it remains largely a male-dominant artform, at least from the lens of spatial and social positioning of artisans. An attempt to study the weaknesses and challenges faced by artisans engaged in intricate and delicate works of Zari-zardozi reveals myriad issues that lead to vulnerable imbalance. The handicraft industry is labelled backwards and inferior; issues such as illiteracy, ignorance, abject poverty, dependency on the middlemen, information-gap between artisans and consumers, lack of awareness and knowledge about the market, lack of governmental support making a few of the arts/crafts to lose their sheen in the rapid industrialisation (Priya, 2021). This particular analysis, however, neglects the participation of women Zardozi artisans.

This can marginally be attributed to the fact that Muslim women, especially from low-income groups, having largely been uneducated and married, are

forced to occupy a “behind the scenes” role to support the craft. Most women pick up Zardozi to contribute to income generation in the absence of proper education and lack of other inclusive livelihood opportunities. The challenge for the Government is not only how to improve the condition of the female artisans, but more importantly, to preserve these traditional handicraft products and artisans from extinction.

2. Ethnographic Evolution of Zardozi in India

The history of Zardozi is intertwined with the history of Muslim culture in India. Zardozi or Zari work is a signature embroidery artform with Persian origins dating back to the thirteenth century. The origins of Zardozi as a craft can be traced back to the rise of Islam in Asia. The demand for specific gold and silver threadwork can be attributed to the emergence of Mughal culture, where Zardozi reached its zenith and spread not just across India, but globally.

Although embroidery finds mentions even in the Vedas and can be traced back to the evolution of Indian history, it was only the advancements under the Mughal era that placed the craft as a unique aesthetic emerging from the influences of the rich courts of noblemen and women (Biswas, 2020). In *Futuhat-i-Firoz Shahi*, the memoirs of Firoz Shah Tughlaq not only identified the different types of clothing and their use but perhaps also, for the first time, coined the word “zardozi” (“zar” for gold and “dozi” for work). The establishment of workshops or *karkhanas* during this period led to further institutionalisation of the art form (Bhandari, 2015).

Myths and legends about the origins of Zardozi continue to serve and pass on through thin threads. The exact history of its origin remains largely untold or unknown; however, memories of many Sultanate period historians confirm the embellishment and extravagance of the art and its period.

Accounts of Francois Bernier and Vasco da Gama are testaments of the flourishing history of art during the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries (Bukhari & Naeem, 2021). However, much of this financial and cultural support for the arts and literature was dismantled with the 1857 Revolt and the subsequent violent backlash against the Muslim populace. Furthermore, myths about the Muslim community have resulted in the community being isolated, struggling to get recognition of its national identity and preservation of its cultural milieu. (Verma, 1994)

In the nineteenth and twentieth centuries, industrialisation, followed by globalisation, led to the massive export of textile and hand-made products, shrinking the domestic market and leaving artisans to compete for quality and access to opportunities. For some, the beginning of the sharp decline in demand for *asli zardozi* (real gold work) and the rise of sub-standard work, occurred in tandem with the collapse of the Soviet Union which was a major buyer of Zardozi embroidered products.

Zardozi products have a high international market, and their history is laden with Muslim men and women who sustained it over the years in areas that are currently marred with economic and religious strife. There is still a high-luxury market for Zardozi textiles, however, the work hugely remains demand-based and is fostered by extremely low wages for the workers who toil with the needle and the thread.

Muslims have significantly contributed to the enriching of India's art, culture and heritage yet they are majorly marginalised from inclusively participating in nation-building activities. What once was a glimmer of grandiose is now a lost art being sustained by those who have been neglected and forgotten.

Many challenges continue to deter the active participation of the Muslim community from the market, further disabling them to access equal opportunities. Juxtaposing the craft's royal history, the plight of local artisans, especially Muslim women, is marred with economic distress, social imbalances and a lack of inclusive opportunities.

3. The Muslim Community in India – An Overview

Muslims account for one of the largest minorities in India which is home to the third-largest Muslim population in the world. The Sachar Committee Report, 2006, commissioned under Prime Minister Manmohan Singh, presented critical findings concerning the socio-economic marginalisation of the Muslim community, placing them far behind other Socio-Religious Communities (SRCs) in the areas of education, employment, access to credit, access to social and physical infrastructure and political representation. The report also stated that 25 per cent of the total school-going Muslim children either do not reach/have access to school or are left out (Sachar, 2006).

One sentence of the Sachar Committee Report which was alarmingly shocking stated how “fearing for their security, Muslims are increasingly resorting to living in ghettos across the country” (Sachar et al., 2006: 14). The report still serves as testimony to decades of institutional neglect and bias that has left the country's Muslims systematically segmented and vulnerable. Over the years, Muslims have been further excluded from equal opportunities and access to education and employment and isolated further. This is validated by consistent high dropout rates and low literacy levels among the community.

Literacy rates among the Muslim communities have persistently been lower than the national average. Furthermore, especially in the last decade, rampant reports of Muslims being segregated on religious lines have further isolated them as a community who are treated even worse than the scheduled castes and tribes. While the latter have institutional frameworks to safeguard their representation, Muslims have been resorting to migration and systematic marginalisation by choice or by design.

Even after a decade of the Sachar Committee recommendations, the Muslims in India lag in all spheres of education (Muhammed, 2020). Gayer and Jaffrelot have studied the empirical emergence of socio-spatial positioning of Muslims in India and have found the pull effects of economic and social clustering in the form of segregated and dilapidated neighbourhoods or “ghettos” across the country (Jaffrelot & Gayer, 2012).

This voluntary and forced clustering is also due to the wider “mental maps” through which Muslims experience, perceive, and judge their city. Such mental maps specifically help to uncover historical trajectories, feelings of insecurity and the future expectations of people regarding their cities – irrespective of quantitative degrees of segregation (Susewind, 2017). The proportion of Muslims in cultivation and agricultural activities is less than among their Hindu counterparts (Patel, 2013). Muslims continue to be highly concentrated in the industrial sector and low-quality employment such as craft and related works, plants and machine operators and elementary occupations (Naik, Khan, & Verma, 2017).

It is within these segmented clusters and mental associations of the community, where crafts like Zardozi are still sustaining livelihoods, albeit not thrivingly.

4. Veiled and Valiant – The Muslim Women of Unorganized Sector in India

42.7% of Muslims in India are illiterate. This is the highest illiteracy rate for any single religious community in the country (The Wire, 2016). Under the ambit of employment and education, Muslim women fare far behind their counterparts and other female communities.

While historically there has always been a gap between the boys and girls in India, the case of Muslim women has been yawning (Bano, 2017). India’s Female Labour Force Participation Rate (LFPR)—the share of working-age women who report either being employed or being available for work—fell to a historic low of 23 per cent in 2017-18, meaning that over three out of four women over the age of 15 in India are neither working nor seeking work. This would imply that they are most likely running the house and taking care of children (S, 2019).

Unfortunately, Indian Muslim women face the double disadvantage of being female and Muslim (Lahiri & Shadab, 2021). Many challenges continue to deter Muslim women from accessing equal opportunities. External ecosystems and patriarchal setups within households have left Muslim women far behind. Poverty, illiteracy, prejudices, stereotypes, and domestic duties have further led to deprivation and discrimination and marginalisation of Muslim women in India.

Post-independence feminist scholars have made persuasive arguments that women's agency is not only wielded in resistance to relations of domination, but also in the capacity to act according to the exigencies of a specific socio-cultural context (Legg, 2003). Post- Partition, Muslim women exercised agency and claimed space and belonging in everyday negotiations and strategies for survival by contributing to family income and small capitalism (Datta, 2021).

Women adopted traditional nurturing roles as well as transformed previous duties into new techniques of protest such as spinning, stitching or sewing, thereby constructing political home spaces. It is noteworthy to analyse this shift through the lens of present-day Zardozi production within low-income Muslim households. The afterlives of colonial-era patriarchal work culture, including the assumption that women's work is less skilled or less valuable than that of men and that labouring in public lacks respectability, continue to haunt the lives of women artisans and industrial workers. (Lanzillo & Kumar, 2021)

The hypothesis is that Zardozi is a male-dominated art but are women working in silos that have been neglected and deprived of their due wages and acknowledgement. This can marginally be attributed to the fact that Muslim women, especially from low-income groups, having largely been uneducated and married, are forced to occupy a "behind the scenes" role to support the craft. These are the missing Muslim women of Zardozi.

5. Research Objectives

The paper aims to trace the history of Zardozi and its women by assessing the working conditions of Muslim Zardozi women artisans. More specifically:

- To study in tandem, the ethnographic evolution of Zardozi and present-day working conditions of artisans.
- To assess perceptions, challenges and opportunities within the ambit of Muslim women engaged as Zardozi workers in the rural/semi-urban clusters and blocks of Farrukhabad (UP) and regions of Delhi.
- To understand the disparities between male and female Zardozi workers.
- To understand why women do not engage and participate directly with the craft beyond their homes. Does the answer lie beyond patriarchy?

6. Research Methodology

The study employs mixed methods of research design. It builds on the empirical findings of fieldwork undertaken in the Farrukhabad district between 2018 and 2021 by combining primary and secondary research findings. The approach takes artisans and their spatial positioning as a tool of enquiry.

For the purpose of this paper, a total of 51 respondents were interviewed between February to April 2022. FGDs and one-on-one interviews were conducted over the phone and in-person via door-to-door visits by the field teams of E&H Foundation through google forms; data was analysed and visualised using statistical tools on excel. Conversations with other stakeholders (such as retailers or workshop owners) and migrant workers were also undertaken.

The respondents were ensured to be involved where most Zari artisans are concentrated. These involved rural slums of Shamsabad block in the Farrukhabad district of Uttar Pradesh as well as semi-urban areas of Shahpurhat and Maharani Bagh in New Delhi.

7. Challenges and Limitations

In light of COVID contingency, telephonic interviews were conducted initially. This posed many challenges as men usually take the phone to work and women do not have personal gadgets. Some women were not comfortable or confident to speak over the phone. Some artisans were interviewed in the presence of their employers in Karkhanas and may have been hesitant in discussing challenges at length. Eventually, door-to-door interviews were conducted along with GDs and virtual interviews.

8. A Summary in Pictures

Some glimpses of encounters with Zardozi artisans are summarised in the pictures below. Evidently, men can be spotted in Karkhanas, while women can be spotted working alone or in groups within homes or four walls.

Image 1: Intricate Zardozi Patterns (2018)

Image 2: Typical Karkhanas where men work (2018)

Image 3: Women artisans working together within homes (2019)

Image 3: Women artisans working together within homes (2019)

Image 2: Typical Karkhanas where men work (2018)

9. Findings and Analysis

Table 1 highlights the demographic distribution across variability. Of all respondents, 80 per cent were women and 20 per cent were men; 98 per cent were Muslim. More than 85 per cent of respondents were in the age group of 25-34 or above the age of 35. Over 50 per cent of the respondents had either never been to school or were briefly enrolled and dropped out.

While 90 per cent of the artisans were operating out of their households, only 10 per cent were employed in the workshops or Karkhanas. Data validates the fact that most Muslim women involved in Zardozi operate out of their homes.

84 per cent of respondents were based in rural areas where Zardozi is the only form of labour or employment that they can access or afford.

9.1. Lower than low-wages

Zardozi artisans are usually at the mercy of the market. Work is largely demand-based and erratic. Wages are in the form of piece-based compensation and commissions. Artisans struggle to sustain stable livelihoods with sporadic salaries and irregular demand for embroidery work. Table 2 reveals that 90% of artisans are part-time workers or freelancers (those who operate out of their homes – mostly women) and are paid in cash as per completion of piece-based orders.

Wages are paid post completion of orders in Nakad (cash). There is no system of monthly or daily wages for Zardozi artisans. Women artisans are usually paid per Kali (embroidered bud). The income per piece ranges from INR 150 to INR 700 depending on the design and depth of embroidery. One such piece may take up to 10 days of work and may be undertaken by three to ten artisans

collectively. Women earn anywhere between INR 2000 to INR 4000 monthly which they may have to further split among other women (relatives or in-laws etc). Men, on the other hand, get paid INR 500 to up to INR 1200 per piece depending on the hours they put in.

There is a widening pay gap between not only the wages but also the tools and resources men and women involved in the craft employ to finish their work. Even the Attas (wooden frames) on which they perform the intricate embroidery are either their family's or husband's or employer's (Figure 1).

Figure 1 - Do you own the Atta (wooded frame) or use someone else's'

9.2. Lack of Collective Bargaining Power or Unionism

In many cases, women do not have a direct income and sustain on a supplementary income which is paid to the males further limiting their direct participation with the labour force. Financial freedoms of Muslim women are restricted and dependent on their counterparts unless in the case of widows. Even the earned income which is usually paid per-piece is allotted to the husband to run the household. This further limits their participation in domestic decision-making.

Retailers or employers mostly consist of Mohallewalas (community people), middlemen, Karkhana owners are directly in touch with city-vendors, local community members, neighbours, agents, relatives, family members, or other male artisans employed at workshops including husbands and brothers. This increases women's dependency on their spouses and relatives for getting work.

“Wo Humse Kamate Hain, Hum Unse Nahi Kamate”

(They earn from us, we don't earn from them) - Nazia, 22, Farrukhabad

9.3. Lack of other opportunities or means of livelihood generation

Under these circumstances, many artisans resort to engaging in alternate livelihood activities. 14 per cent of the respondents worked an additional job for added income. (Figure 2). These mostly include men. Only two women reported undertaking additional jobs like stitching work or labouring at kilns.

Figure 2 - Do you work any other job apart from Zardozi

While men get paid more and have access to other employment opportunities like farming, labour work etc., women are left tending to household chores and awaiting the wedding seasons to double up their labours or assist their husbands with orders. On further enquiry, women revealed that due to a lack of other skills or opportunities, they struggle to sustain their families and contribute meaningfully to income generation.

9.4. The learned-unlearned and art as their last resort

The art of Zardozi is passed on through generations like heritage and heirlooms. The skill is acquired through observation. It was noted during the study that Muslim children are taught traditional livelihood forms in the family from a very young age.

Respondents mentioned cultivating the skill from their grandparents, Ammi (mother), Abbu (father), elder brothers or sisters, relatives, neighbours, community members, husbands and in-laws. In most cases, they learnt the art by mere observation and simply by being around elders who were doing the craft; yet, ironically still identified themselves as “unlearned” or talentless.

Women artisans, especially, referred to themselves as labourers, or mazdoor (an unskilled labourer), instead of artisans, even when they were highly

skilled. On average, respondents were working for 13 years in their current profession and still considered their work unskilled. Zardozi, hence, is considered less of a hunar (talent or skill) and more of a last resort.

9.5. Starting young - All hands on the cloth

In a traditional Zardozi household, children grow up watching, and often assisting, elders with their work. Children's contribution to family income starts early. 41 per cent of respondents (all women) reported getting some assistance or support from their children. 72 per cent of these children were girls, while 14 per cent were boys and in 14 per cent of the cases, both were boys and girls. (Figures 3 & 4)

Figure 3 - Is any child employed as Zari worker or assisting with Zardozi?

Figure 4 - Gender of the child employed or assisting with Zardozi work

Respondents' average age at which they started working as an artisan was 16 years. Most artisans mentioned that they would ideally not want their kids to follow their path, reporting higher ambition and skilled work for them. These conditions and perceptions further demotivate the next generation of artisans from being associated with the historical craft and force them to look for alternative opportunities making Zardozi a vanishing art form.

9.6. The Painful Physicality of Zardozi

The tools of the embroiderer include thread, frames, needles, cutters, and fabric. And bodies. (Graziani Giles, 2021) Even after the sun is set, dinner is served and kids are asleep; men and women continue to toil till midnight. Women more so since their days are interrupted and integrated with myriad domestic duties such as cooking, cleaning, and taking care of the children or elders, among others.

“At night, we are able to concentrate better. Sometimes, we have dinner post-midnight after wrapping up work” – Santara, 27, Shahpurjat, New Delhi

Intricate work with the thread and needle demands hours to be still and working. While most women complained of eye problems, others mentioned that they frequently suffer back pains, along with sore or numb arms and hands. Male artisans also reported similar pain from the labour. However, it is worthy to note that women have double burdens; they work equally hard to sustain households and contribute to income generation and yet are largely unaccounted for in the ecosystem of Zardozi.

Nazar Ka Kaam Hai Aur Humari Nazar Kamzor Hai. Raat Ko Dikhta Nahi To Din Me Hi Kaam Karte Hai” (It’s the eyes that employ and since I have weak eyesight, I prefer to work in daylight and can’t work post-sunset) – Shabeena, 35, Farrukhabad

On an average, women spent four hours performing household chores and duties in addition to working six to seven hours on average doing Zardozi each day. They complained of not being able to work at par with men because of these commitments and heightened burden of labour.

9.7. Positions, Perceptions and Predispositions of Female Zardozi Artisans

Zardozi is seen as *Majboori Ki Mazdoori* (labour of helplessness). Instead of pride, it’s a predisposition, a compromise to sustain and support income. While men are perceived as employing the more complex or “learned” form of embroidery work, women usually perceive themselves as “sub-standard” or assistant workers as opposed to artisans in any way. Despite this belief, they still were cognizant of the disparities in income against the work they clock in. When asked if women get paid at par with men of Zardozi, 71 per cent disagreed, while 21 per cent were not sure. (Figure 5)

Figure 5 - Do you think women get paid at par with their husbands/other male members in the community doing Zardozi?

When asked if they would like to operate out of women-led *Karkhanas*, 37 per cent said yes, 20 per cent were not sure and 43 per cent said no (Figure 6). Those who disagreed with the idea mentioned reasons such as household commitments, taking care of children, disapproval of husbands or family members to go out for work or lack of community support. While those who said yes or not sure, stated they would go if other women within the community also go and if *Karkhanas* can be established within 100 metres to 1 km of their households.

Figure 6 - Would you like to go to a women-led *Karkhanas* to operate out of in your locality?

9.8. Migration patterns and behaviours

29 per cent of respondents, mostly men, said they had, at some point, moved to other nearby cities like Delhi or Jaipur in search of better opportunities and higher wages (Figure 7). However, most returned to their respective villages except for the artisans working in Delhi who had migrated from West Bengal or Bihar. The geographical distribution of artisan's hometowns is depicted in Figure 8.

Figure 7 - If ever migrated for work, or better opportunity?

Figure 8 - Hometown

Most of these artisans who had hometowns in West Bengal, Bihar, or other parts of UP were either migrant workers or women who had accompanied their husbands to other locations post-marriage. Return migrations were mostly a result of double burdens of rents and city segregations, as well as COVID.

Urban Muslims are even further isolated from their communities and bear the brunt of added expenses on living, running the household as well as educating their children. This further forces such artisans to mentally map their place in cities and being shunned out of equal opportunities and in many cases, resorting to forced migration back to villages.

9.9. COVID and its impact on Zardozi

COVID pushed many artisans beyond the margins, causing major distress and deprivation. In areas like Farrukahabd, where Zardozi is a major form of livelihood generation for many families, lockdowns put many out of work. 96 per cent of respondents did not have a paying job in the initial months of lockdown in 2020 (Figure 9).

Figure 9 - Did you have a paying job in COVID?

At the peak of COVID, migrant workers had moved back and paltry savings were exhausted. Furthermore, wages have gone down massively over the last few months. 65 per cent of respondents revealed they were receiving lower wages post-COVID (Figure 10).

Figure 10 - Did you get lower wages during/post COVID?

There is a sincere need to protect these artisans by ensuring entitlements and support in the form of benefits, training support and access to markets.

9.10. Need for social protection of Zardozi artisans

There are many policies, programmes and provisions in place by the state to preserve various art forms and cultures and multiple schemes to ensure the social protection of artisans. Zardozi is a recognised craft under the Ministry of Textiles. Programs and schemes like the National Handicraft Development Project (NHDP) and Baba Saheb Ambedkar Hastshilp Vikas Yojana (AHVY) are in place to provide assistance and support to artisans. Yet, awareness around them remains alarmingly low.

Not even one respondent was aware of any of these schemes or was enrolled in them (Figures 11 & 12). Efforts need to be undertaken to link these artisans, especially female artisans to various social protection schemes; especially under a diminishing market and artform that is further threatened with uncertainties like COVID and a dynamically evolving fashion and competitive textile industry.

Figure 11 - Do you know of any schemes or provisions for Zardozi Workers?

Figure 12 - Any handicrafts specific government schemes enrolled in?

Furthermore, under the recent integration of the ODOP Scheme, Lucknow Chikankari and Zardozi work is exported nationally and globally (Yadav et al., 2022). The scheme is expected to help revive and promote traditional Indian industries that have been struggling to compete with modern mass-produced products. But smaller districts like Farrukhabad are still not recognised for producing high-quality Zardozi embroidery work

10. Conclusion

Zardozi has predominantly been a Muslim-led artform with a rich history, yet the present-day conditions of artisans and the market have deteriorated the craft and turned it into a diminishing artform. Furthermore, socio-economic conditions of Muslims have forced the community into ghettos where these arts are equally thriving and vanishing at the margins.

From a spatial positioning, Zardozi appears to be a male-dominated craft, however, there are Muslim women working in silos that have been neglected and deprived of their due wages and acknowledgement. They are dependent on males of the households, middlemen, community agents and others to get work and operate within four walls. While most women do not consider themselves as skilled as the men, they still understand the social segregation and economic discrimination that the art fosters.

Conditions of women artisans are troubling since they are not able to participate directly with the opportunities that otherwise accompany the trade of Zardozi. Education, household duties, lack of awareness, traditional set-ups, perceptions and beliefs of their work being sub-standard to men continue to deter Muslim women from breaking the wall ceiling and demanding their due wages or benefits. Most women involved in Zardozi consider it as a means to an end. They believe themselves to be talentless, skill-less, and deeply deprived of any other opportunities.

Sadly, Zardozi, a proud historical artform, has become a burden and a last resort for livelihood for these women. Efforts need to be undertaken to sustain, support and scale Zardozi and link female artisans to various social protection schemes as well as provide them the required training and mentoring to advance their participation in the market and contribute towards income-generation and nation-building.

The Lucknow Zardozi is accorded the Geographical Indication (GI) status. However, Farrukhabad does not have any such authenticity marking despite both regions belonging to the Ganga-Jamuni Tehzeeb.

Muslim women continue to be concentrated in the low-quality employment of Zardozi where they function as invisible enablers and are paid much less with no support from the community or state. They are excluded from both the developmental and economic processes of the craft, being restricted to their homes with lower-than low wages and orthodox perceptions. Over the years, Muslim women have been the backbone of Zardozi often shadowing their husbands and brothers instead of directly engaging with the economic opportunities that have the potential to liberate them and promote their equal participation.

II. Recommendations

To preserve the art and culture of a vanishing art form and to increase Muslim women's participation in the trade of Zardozi with multi-cultural and multi-religious history, the following recommendations can be considered:

- Linking Zardozi artisans, especially Muslim women, to relevant social protection schemes like AHVY and others.
- Recognising and integrating the district of Farrukhabad as a major cluster for producing high-quality Zardozi embroidery work nationally and internationally under the One District One Product (ODOP) scheme.
- Promoting local groups and training support centres or Zardozi cooperatives within UP and Delhi.
- Assistance from civil society organisations and influential community members can be leveraged to organise and link female artisans with further opportunities like trade fairs or access to markets.
- Local female-led groups and women-led Karkhanas can be considered to promote regional craft in hamlets and within villages.
- Micro enterprises that are women-led and women-run can be established to promote the art of Zardozi, provide a sustainable and stable means of income generation and protect female artisans.

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